

Mn and Au redox mediators in ZnCl₂ water-in-salt electrolytes: Implications for Zn-ion battery chemistry

Ladislav Kavan^{a,b,*}, Tařana Supiřkova^a, Věra Mansfeldova^a, Marketa Zukalova^a,
Zuzana Vlckova Živcova^a, Felix T. Eickemeyer^b, Michael Graetzel^b

^a Heyrovsky Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Dolejškova 3, 18200 Prague 8, Czech Republic

^b Laboratory of Photonics and Interfaces, Institute of Chemical Sciences and Engineering, Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne, CH-1015, Lausanne, Switzerland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Zinc-ion battery
Water in salt electrolyte
Zinc chloride
Manganese chloride
Tetrachloroauric acid

ABSTRACT

Redox mediators in water-in-salt electrolytes (WiSE) offer a compelling platform for durable, safe, and efficient Zn-ion battery. Here we investigate two model systems: MnCl₂ and HAuCl₄ dissolved in 15 m ZnCl₂. Using a carbon positive electrode enables areal capacities of approx. 1 mAh/cm², outperforming traditional electrodes with solid thin-film materials, e.g., phosphate olivines. This capacity is available in a WiSE volume, which fits the standard 2032 coin cell. The WiSE environment substantially alleviates the “dead MnO₂” problem, while γ-MnO₂ is generated by anodic oxidation of Mn²⁺ over a broad potential region. The charge transfer is diffusion-limited, with ion transport primarily controlled by the viscosity of the WiSE. Remarkably, Au and Mn display strikingly similar electrochemical signatures, each producing broad, asymmetric voltammetric peaks with a formal potential near 1.7 V vs Zn²⁺/Zn, despite Mn redox couples being shifted by ca. 0.7 V below their standard potentials. The observed potential shifts arise from chloromanganate formation as well as from WiSE-specific effects. The potentials are conveniently referenced to the Ru(NH₃)₆^{3+/2+} couple, which is essentially insensitive to ZnCl₂ concentration. Gold undergoes rapid oxidative dissolution to AuCl₄. The Au-Zn alloys are identified by distinct features at anodic stripping, as well as by SEM, EDX and XPS. These findings highlight both the opportunities and mechanistic complexities of liquid-phase redox mediators for high-capacity Zn-ion energy-storage systems with WiSE.

1. Introduction

The rechargeable aqueous Zn-ion batteries, pioneered by Shoji et al. [1] and Xu et al. [2], attract attention for addressing the safety/cost/sustainability issues of the currently dominating technology, i. e., Li-ion [3–13]. The negative electrode in these batteries is almost always Zn metal, acting through the stripping/plating charge-transfer:

(E^0 is the tabled standard redox potential). Reaction (1) is virtually simple, but is complicated by dendrite formation, parasitic H₂ evolution, corrosion, and substrate dependence [14–21].

The interfacial processes at the positive electrode consist either in a traditional Zn²⁺ intercalation into, e.g. α-MnO₂ [1,2,22]:

(which is, however, far from being a simple topotactic intercalation [22]) or in a “dual-ion” chemistry. In the latter case, the intercalation of electrolyte counter-anions (such as ClO₄) into graphite is at play in the positive electrode [23]. Another option is the Zn/Li dual-ion process, employing the known materials from Li-ion batteries, such as LiFePO₄ (olivine; LFP) [24–28]:

The use of highly concentrated aqueous solutions for Zn-ion batteries is rationalized by the fact that the absence of free water molecules in the solution extends the electrochemical stability window, and impedes the Zn-dendrite formation, thus improving the coulombic efficiency of the negative electrode. This strategy was pioneered in 2018 by Wang et al. [29], and since then, it has developed significantly [8–11,14–16,21,23,24,30–32]. Side reactions on the Zn electrode were also mitigated by hydrogels [33], protective polymer films [28], separator modifications

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: kavan@jh-inst.cas.cz (L. Kavan).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2026.148513>

Received 19 December 2025; Received in revised form 15 February 2026; Accepted 21 February 2026

Available online 22 February 2026

0013-4686/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

[34], or electrolyte additives [35,36]. (Note a typo in [36]: ‘gluconate’ was confused with ‘gallium’). Recently, Vazques et al. [37] found that a local pH increase and sluggish water transport cause the enhancement of the electrochemical stability window in highly concentrated electrolyte solutions.

Zinc chloride is exceptional for these applications thanks to its extreme solubility [38]. The hydrate $\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is liquid for $n \approx 2$ [39]. Solutions having $2 < n < 3$ are called “molten hydrates”. The next category of highly saturated solutions is the ‘water-in-salt’ (WiSE), which is defined by the mass ratio of salt/ H_2O exceeding one; for ZnCl_2 , these ratios equal: $3 < n < 7.6$. The remaining solutions ($n > 7.6$ for ZnCl_2) are the usual (salt-in-water) media, which are used ubiquitously in electrochemistry. Raman and IR spectroscopy [38,39], neutron- and X-ray diffraction [39] identified an array of species, present in the highly concentrated ZnCl_2 solutions. The dominating structures are octahedral complexes $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{6-x}\text{Cl}_x]^{2-x}$ and tetrahedral complexes $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{4-x}\text{Cl}_x]^{2-x}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 4$). Of particular interest is the congruently melting (at 6 °C) phase for $n = 3$: $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6][\text{ZnCl}_4]$, which behaves, actually, like an ionic liquid. It exhibits extraordinary hydrogen-bond-donating ability, rapid dissolution of cellulose and high anti-freezing ability [40].

Redox mediators, such as $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ or I_3/I^- were introduced to the Zn-Mn battery to facilitate the MnO_2 dissolution, and mitigate the problem of “dead MnO_2 ” [41]. A direct implementation of Mn-based redox couples as mediators remains challenging. This strategy is inspired by (i) “cathode-free” battery architectures [22] and (ii) all-manganese redox-flow batteries [42,43]. They, however, still suffer from problems associated with the hydrolytic disproportionation of Mn^{3+} to Mn^{2+} and solid MnO_2 , which progressively occlude active reaction sites and degrade the capacity. Consequently, rechargeable Zn/ MnO_2 batteries still face key challenges that contrast sharply with the historical and commercial success of their primary counterparts [44]. Other attempts to mitigate the MnO_2 -driven passivation included coordination engineering using, e.g., EDTA or inorganic additives, such as $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ [42], Ti^{IV} or V^{V} [43]. Huang et al. [32] introduced a highly concentrated 46.5 m (m = molality) solution containing acetates of Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and NH_4^+ in ammonia. Their battery with $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4/\text{Mn}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{2+}$ couple as a positive electrode provided 10 mAh/cm² capacity over 200 cycles. Here, we simplified this concept using MnCl_2 in 15 m ZnCl_2 (WiSE). Furthermore, our system is favored by ca. 0.2 V larger voltage.

The gold-based redox mediators are not common in commercial Zn-batteries for obvious cost and stability issues. Although we do not aim to develop any Zn-Au battery, studies of this system address practical challenges that extend beyond academic curiosity. For example, Au-coating suppressed dendrite growth on Zn by forming a zincophilic Zn_3Au alloy, thereby improving the performance of Zn/ NaV_3O_8 batteries [45]. While the electrochemistry of AuCl_4^- in conventional media, including ionic liquids, is scrutinized [46], its behavior in WiSE remains greatly unexplored. Comparing the Au- and Mn-based redox mediators provides fundamental insight into practical battery systems that rely on Mn^{2+} oxidation as the primary process at the positive electrode.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials and electrodes

Anhydrous ZnCl_2 was from Sigma Aldrich (puriss, p.a.); selected as the best-quality product among various suppliers [21]. It was dried in a vacuum at 150 °C overnight, and subsequently dissolved in water to a concentration of 15 m. The density of this WiSE was determined by weighing a known pipetted volume of the liquid, and was found to be 1.85 g/cm³, consistent with the literature [47]. $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\geq 99\%$, p.a.) was from Carl Roth, GmbH. Other chemicals were from Sigma Aldrich and used as received. The carbon black, C65, electrode was mounted using TorrSeal epoxy. The glass-like carbon (dia. 3 mm)

electrode was from Metrohm. KynarFlex 2801 fluoropolymer powder was from Arkema. Zinc (0.25 mm sheet, 99.99 %), was from Goodfellow, Ltd. Titanium foil, grade 2 (0.1 mm thickness) was from G24i, Ltd. It was cleaned by boiling 20 % HCl, washed with copious amounts of water and dried. Highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG; from Bruker, grade ZYB) was peeled off by Scotch tape, contacted on the exposed side by a gold strip (0.05 mm thick, Goodfellow) and mounted by hot-pressing into laminating foils as detailed elsewhere [48]. The active electrode area was defined by a hole (2 mm in diameter) which was cut in the upper laminating foil (see Fig. S1 in the ESI).

A porous carbon electrode was prepared from a mixture of 95 wt % carbon black (C65) and 5 wt % of KynarFlex, the latter was added in the form of a 10 % solution in N-methyl pyrrolidone. The mixture was subsequently diluted by this solvent to a consistency of viscous paste, homogenized by sonication and stirred overnight. The slurry was coated by doctor blading on the Ti substrate, using the Kapton adhesive tape for the protection of the edges. The electrodes were finally dried at 120 °C in vacuum [21].

2.2. Methods

Electrochemical experiments were carried out using a BioLogic SP300 potentiostat. The reference and counter-electrodes were from Zn-foil. In some cases, the Ag/AgCl reference (sat. KCl from Metrohm; $E^0 = 0.197$ V) was also used. The experimentally found potential difference of Zn^{2+}/Zn and Ag/AgCl in 15 m ZnCl_2 (WiSE) was -0.689 V. For easier notation, the potentials in volts referenced to the Ag/AgCl electrode are further labeled V_{AgCl} and the potentials referenced to Zn^{2+}/Zn are labeled V_{Zn} . The standard electrochemical potentials (vs. SHE) are edited in V without a subscript. To ensure strictly reproducible conditions, the WiSE was purged with Ar, and electrochemical measurements were performed in a closed electrochemical cell under an Ar atmosphere. Nevertheless, the presence of atmospheric oxygen is not detrimental to most of the electrochemical measurements reported here. The H-shaped electrochemical cell with a Zn-negative electrode and carbon-based positive electrode was used for modeling the battery tests (Fig. S2, ESI). The H-cell was completed by a glass-fiber separator (Whatman GF/D [49]). Note that a filter paper (cellulose) cannot be used as a separator, because it quickly dissolves in ZnCl_2 -based WiSE [40].

In situ Raman spectroelectrochemistry employed a glass cell with Au or HOPG working electrodes and Zn as both reference and counter electrodes in the WiSE electrolyte (15 m ZnCl_2 ; pure or mixed with 0.2 m MnCl_2). The potential was controlled with an CompactStat potentiostat (Ivium Technologies, BV). Raman spectra were excited with a He-Ne laser (1.96 eV) and recorded using a LabRAM HR spectrometer (Horiba Jobin-Yvon) interfaced to an Olympus microscope (100 × objective). Spectra were acquired simultaneously with the electrochemical measurements. The spectrometer was calibrated using the F_{1g} mode of Si at 520.2 cm⁻¹.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies were performed using a JEOL JSM 6510LV microscope, accelerating voltage 25 kV. Elemental analysis was performed using an Oxford Instruments Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) detector. EDX measurements were evaluated by the INCA software. X-ray photoelectron spectra (XPS) were measured using a SPECS Surface Nano Analysis System, equipped with the Al $\text{K}\alpha$ X-ray source. Optical (UV-Vis) spectra were measured by an UV-1800 UV-vis spectrometer (Shimadzu, Japan) using a 1-cm quartz cell.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Manganese electrochemistry in WiSE

Our earlier work [21] disclosed that a trace amount (ca. 0.1 wt %) of Mn impurity in commercial ZnCl_2 , exhibited specific electrochemical activity, which could be easily confused with that of the active electrode materials. To explore this effect in depth, Fig. 1 shows five subsequent

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of HOPG in 15 m ZnCl_2 + 0.2 m MnCl_2 (five initial cycles at the scan rate of 50 mV/s). Chart [A] shows the initial two cycles, chart [B] shows the subsequent three cycles. The voltammogram for the 5th cycle (dashed curve) was zoomed out by a factor of 0.2. Inset in chart [A] shows the integral voltammetry charge of Mn-related peaks (open points = anodic, crosses = cathodic). Arrows point at the assumed redox couples.

cyclic voltammograms of a basal-plane HOPG electrode in 15 m ZnCl_2 + 0.2 m MnCl_2 . The HOPG electrode has been selected as a proxy of a clean carbonaceous surface for investigating electrochemical reactions at well-defined conditions. Fig. 1 and additional voltammograms, shown in Fig. S3 (ESI), illustrate the complex electrochemistry of manganese [42, 43]. In general, the oxidation of Mn^{2+} starts from a one-electron reaction:

The associated $d^5 - d^4$ transformation provides (for high-spin octahedral complexes) a strongly Jahn-Teller distorted Mn^{3+} species, which is prone to hydrolytic disproportionation [50]:

The MnO_2 formed in reaction (5), either in colloidal solution or as a solid deposit [42,43], can trigger Zn^{2+} -insertion similar to that shown above (see Eq. 2). The insertion reactions are complicated by a polymorphism of MnO_2 (α - and δ -phases are considered to be active for Zn^{2+} -insertion). Other possible transformations of MnO_2 are conversion reactions, producing, e.g., ZnMn_3O_4 , and co-insertion of H^+ , whose mechanism is still controversial. In addition, direct electrochemical redox reactions of MnO_2 can occur, either by reduction to Mn^{2+} (Eq. 6) [22] or by oxidation to permanganate (Eq. 7):

While reaction (5) is a net chemical transformation without any electrochemical signature, the other reactions (4, 6 and 7) are charge-transfer processes, which should be distinguishable electrochemically. In accord with the earlier work in 5 M H_2SO_4 [43], we assign the cathodic peak in Fig. 1A (1st scan) at $\approx 1.2 \text{ V}_{\text{Zn}}$ to the $\text{MnO}_2/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ reduction (Eq. 6; the corresponding reduction peak in H_2SO_4 was reported to be at 1.12 V vs. SHE [43]). The next cathodic peak near 1.5 V_{Zn} corresponds to the $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ transformation (Eq. 4).

For accurate comparison, we need to recalculate the reference potential of our Zn^{2+}/Zn electrode in WiSE. The found density of WiSE (1.85 g/cm³, see Experimental Section) and the Zn^{2+} concentration, 15 m (molality), translate into $[\text{Zn}^{2+}] = 9.1 \text{ M}$ (molarity; note that these two units are sometimes confused [38]). The activity coefficients can significantly deviate from one in superconcentrated electrolyte

solutions, which complicates the deciphering of Nernstian shifts [51, 52]. If we neglect the enhancement of the activity coefficient in WiSE, the potential of our reference electrode would equal:

$$E_{\text{WiSE}}^{\text{Zn}} = E^0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \{ \gamma \cdot [\text{Zn}^{2+}] \} \approx -0.73 \text{ V vs. SHE} \quad (8)$$

For a reversible simultaneous two-electron process, the cathodic peaks are downshifted by 15 mV against the standard potentials. Yet, neither this effect nor the Nernstian correction (Eq. 8) contribute markedly to the observed difference of experimental potentials. All three cathodic peaks found in our WiSE (Fig. 1) are downshifted, in the SHE scale, by $\approx 0.7 \text{ V}$ as compared to the corresponding peaks, which were reported for the glass-like carbon electrode in 5 M H_2SO_4 [43], and similarly to the values of standard redox potentials shown above.

A plausible rationale is the formation of chloromanganate complexes, such as MnCl_4^{2-} or $\text{MnCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2-}$ in the ultra-high chloride environment. (Note that Eq. 4–6 implicitly assume the “free” ions, such as $\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+/2+}$). Chloride complexation stabilizes Mn^{2+} far more than Mn^{3+} , thereby shifting the $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ redox potential to lower values [53]. Direct evidence for the presence of chloromanganate species is provided by the ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) in the UV-spectrum at approx. 260 nm wavelength [54]. However, spectral analysis in ZnCl_2 -based WiSE is difficult, because a similar LMCT band is present in the blank solution, too (see Fig. S4). Furthermore, the near absence of free water molecules in the distinctive structure of WiSE (see Introduction) shifts the redox potentials, too [14,15,30,38]. This effect was recently interpreted in terms of “liquid-Madelung” potential shift [52].

The anodic part of the Mn-voltammograms exhibits only two peaks (Fig. 1). In analogy to voltammetry in sulfuric acid media, the peak at 2.2 V_{Zn} , occurring in the first scan, is assignable to permanganate (MnO_4^-) formation (Eq. 7). The peak at 1.8 V_{Zn} represents a superposition of two oxidative reactions described by Eqs. 4, 6. Permanganate is readily confirmed by UV-Vis spectroscopy in 0.5–1 M H_2SO_4 by the vibronic 525 nm peak [55,56], as well as by Raman spectroelectrochemistry by the MnO_4^- band at 836 cm^{-1} , which emerges at ca. 1.6 V_{RHE} [56]. In contrast, the optical spectrum of our MnCl_2 - ZnCl_2 solution displays only weak d-d transitions in Mn^{2+} even in diluted ZnCl_2 (0.1 m) and after strong electrochemical oxidation (Fig. S4).

Most notably, Raman spectroelectrochemistry confirms the elusive formation of γ - MnO_2 at all applied potentials from 1.8 to 2.5 V_{Zn}

(Fig. S5). This MnO_2 polymorph is quite stable in acidic media, and has been ubiquitously used in classical primary Zn-batteries. It is actually an intergrowth of pyrolusite ($\beta\text{-MnO}_2$) and ramsdellite (R-MnO_2) phases [55]. The onset of $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2$ growth on HOPG agrees perfectly with the onset of anodic current in the cyclic voltammogram (Fig. 1). Figure S6 shows the SEM images and the results of EDX analysis of the deposit grown on the HOPG electrode. XPS analysis evidences the sole occurrence of Mn(IV) in the deposit (Fig. S7). This material exhibits reasonably reversible charge/discharge cyclability. Integration of current density over time of the voltammograms gives the areal charge/discharge capacity at the HOPG/WiSE interface between 11 and 17 $\mu\text{Ah}/\text{cm}^2$ (Fig. 1).

Consistent with the observations of Hu et al. [56] the absence of MnO_4^- is attributed to comproportionating with Mn^{2+} to form MnO_2 .

This reaction is quite slow in diluted H_2SO_4 , but proceeds rapidly in WiSE for reasons that remain unclear (cf. also Fig S8).

In contrast to the positive electrode, the charge-transfer reactions near the low cut-off potential ($-0.2 \text{V}_{\text{Zn}}$) are relatively simple: we observe just the Zn-plating/stripping on HOPG, which is virtually unperturbed by the presence of Mn^{2+} in WiSE (cf. Figs. 1 and S2). This is an important finding in light of the prospective application for a “cathode-free” Zn-ion battery, in which the active redox mediator (Mn^{2+}) will be dissolved in WiSE (instead of being present as a solid layer covering the positive electrode, like, e.g., in LiMnPO_4 [21]).

Fig. 2 upgrades the data from cyclic voltammetry on HOPG by a comparative study of a glass-like carbon electrode. For the used upper cutoff potential of 2V_{Zn} , the assumed temporary formation of MnO_4^- is avoided (cf. Eq. 7, Fig. 1A). At these conditions, even the less-perfect carbon surface, such as glass-like carbon, provides a well-defined voltammetric response with excellent stability. The charge/discharge reversibility is good, both for the scan-rate test in Fig. 2A (94–100 %) and for the repeated cycling presented in Fig. 2B (90–98 %). Overall, these results show that in ZnCl_2 -WiSE, an upper cutoff potential not significantly exceeding 2V_{Zn} is required to ensure a reliable electrochemical response of manganese at carbon electrodes. Under these conditions, the problem of “dead MnO_2 ” [41] is effectively mitigated. The peak current densities (j_p) follow the Randles-Ševčík equation (cf. Fig. S9):

$$|j_p| = 0.4463nFC \left(\frac{nFvD}{RT} \right)^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

where n is the number of electrons, F is the Faraday constant, C is concentration (in mol/cm^3), v is the scan rate, D is the diffusion coefficient, R is the gas constant and T is temperature. Assuming for simplicity that the peaks correspond solely to the reaction (4) ($n = 1$), then the diffusion coefficient of Mn^{2+} equals $1.5 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$. The tabled diffusion coefficient of Mn^{2+} at infinite dilution is $\approx 0.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$. According to the Stokes-Einstein equation, D is inversely proportional to viscosity (η):

$$D = \frac{k_B T}{6\pi\eta r} \quad (11)$$

k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and r is the hydrodynamic radius of the ion, assuming spherical particles. The viscosity of 15 m ZnCl_2 is about 20 cP, in contrast to 1 cP for a solution at infinite dilution [57]. Hence, Eq. 11 predicts $D = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$ for our WiSE, which agrees reasonably with the experimental value. Both the experimental and molecular dynamics’ simulated self-diffusivities of ions exhibit a linear drop (in semilogarithmic scale) with concentration [58]. Specifically in the Li/Zn dual ion system, the diffusion coefficient of Zn^{2+} decreased from $2.805 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$ (in 1 m solution) to $8.402 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{cm}^2/\text{s}$ in WiSE [24]. In summary, the suppressed diffusion in WiSE appears to be mainly caused by higher viscosity.

Voltammograms similar to those in Fig. 2 are also observed for the carbon black (C65) electrode (Fig. S10, ESI) and the graphite electrode (Fig. S10, ESI). In all cases, we detect a reasonably reversible charge balance of cathodic/anodic reactions, and no obvious interference of the Mn-electrochemistry with the preceding Zn deposition/plating at the carbon surface.

3.2. Hybrid Zn/Mn-redox battery

Inspired by the “cathode-free” [22], all-manganese [42,43] and Zn-vanadium [59] redox-flow batteries, we assembled a hybrid battery, in which the negative electrode is a Zn sheet, and the positive electrode is made from various types of carbons. The solution-based redox mediator, i.e., MnCl_2 , is dissolved in WiSE. The $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ and $\gamma\text{-MnO}_2/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ redox couples serve for charge storage at the carbonaceous positive electrode. The presence of Mn^{2+} in WiSE does not

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of glass-like carbon in 15 m $\text{ZnCl}_2 + 0.2 \text{m MnCl}_2$. [A] Scan-rate dependence; for color coding see annotation. Inset in chart [A] plots the scan-rate dependence of integral voltammetric charge (open points for anodic, crosses for cathodic charge). [B] Ten subsequent cycles at 100 mV/s. Inset in chart [B] shows the integral voltammetric charge (black markers for 200 mV/s, blue markers for 100 mV/s; open points for anodic, crosses for cathodic charge).

interfere with the Zn stripping/plating, even if these reactions occur on the carbon surface instead of Zn-substrate (cf. Section 3.1 and Figs. 1, S10–12). In other words, even very deep cathodic discharging is not detrimental to the carbon electrode, but care should be taken about anodic overcharging, when the side reactions and overall instability of the battery set in (see Section 3.1). To minimize these perturbations, we adjusted the charging time to ≤ 1 hr for the currents ± 4 mA/cm² (Fig. 3B and D).

Fig. 3 summarizes the tests of the two-electrode H-cell (See Fig. S2 and Experimental Section for details). The positive electrode was a thin film (about 0.2 mg/cm²) of carbon black (C65) bonded with PVDF at the Ti-substrate. Additional data obtained with glass-like carbon and graphite electrodes are presented in Figs. S12 and S13, respectively. The initial cycles show an anodic plateau of electrolyte decomposition (presumably Cl₂ evolution) which depends on the electrode material (glass-like carbon, graphite, or carbon black). Yet, these perturbations gradually diminish with continued cycling.

Cyclic voltammogram in Fig. 3A provides the integral charge of 104/90.0 μ Ah/cm² for anodic/cathodic charge, respectively (87 % reversibility). Galvanostatic cycling gave the areal charge/discharge capacity between ca. 1 and 2 mAh/cm² and the reversibility of charging/discharging was between 77 % and 86 % for the cycles 8–21 (Fig. 3C). This capacity is quite high, compared, e.g., to the areal capacity, which was reported for the traditional Zn/LFP batteries [21,28]. Specifically, Wang et al. [28] reported a coin cell with the LFP loading of 0.8 mg/cm² and the capacity of the positive electrode between ca. 150 and 90 mAh/g during 80 galvanostatic cycles at 0.1 A/g (equivalent to approx. 1C rate) in 2 M ZnSO₄. This translates into the areal capacities between ca. 0.12 to 0.07 mAh/cm². Supiňková et al. [21] reported a similar WiSE-based

Zn/LFP system with an LFP loading of 0.3–5 mg/cm² and the specific capacity from 129 to 138 mAh/g during 200 voltammetric scans at a rate mimicking roughly the galvanostatic 3.6 C.

In any case, the areal capacity of our hybrid Zn/Mn battery (with solution-based Mn²⁺) is *by one order of magnitude larger* compared to that of batteries with traditional LFP electrodes [21,28]. This result is promising, considering that it was obtained for a non-optimized, model device. Assuming an overall two-electron charge transfer (γ -MnO₂/Mn²⁺), the areal capacity of 1 mAh/cm² corresponds to 19 μ mol/cm² of Mn. For the concentration of MnCl₂ in our WiSE (0.2 m \approx 0.12 M), the required amount of electrolyte corresponds to approx. 1.6 mm thick layer of WiSE. It is about half of the thickness of a standard 2032 coin cell, confirming that this battery with a solution-based redox mediator is feasible. The areal capacities of the order of magnitude from 0.1 to 10 mAh/cm² have been reported for various cathode-free zinc-electrolytic MnO₂ batteries [22] or Mn(NH₃)₆²⁺ solution-based systems [32], but the application of MnCl₂/ZnCl₂ (WiSE) is here explored for the first time, to the best of our knowledge.

3.3. Gold electrochemistry in WiSE

The electrochemistry of gold was traced inadvertently during the investigation of the Zn/Mn²⁺ system, when the Au current lead accidentally contacted WiSE (see Figs. S1, 3 and Sect. 3.1). To explore this effect in detail, we first tested the Au-disc electrode in 15 m ZnCl₂ (without any deliberately added redox mediator). Fig. 4A shows that gold dissolves very rapidly upon anodic bias in our WiSE, exhibiting a peak current density exceeding 60 mA/cm². This current is nearly doubled compared to the currents for Zn-plating/stripping on the Au-

Fig. 3. H-cell tests in 15 m ZnCl₂ + 0.2 m MnCl₂; the positive electrode is carbon black C65 on Ti substrate; the negative electrode is Zn. [A] cyclic voltammograms, scan rate 50 mV/s; the first and second scans are depicted by full and dashed curves, respectively. [B, D] galvanostatic charge/discharge (± 4 mA/cm²) at different stages of cycling; the maximal time for charging was deliberately set at 1 hr. [C] Cycle life for anodic (red points) and cathodic (blue points) currents.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms at the scan rate of 50 mV/s in 15 m ZnCl₂ (chart A) or in 15 m ZnCl₂ + 0.1 m HAuCl₄ (charts B-D). [A] Au-disc electrode. [B] HOPG-electrode. [C] glass-like carbon electrode. [D] HOPG electrode in H-cell. Unless stated otherwise, the standard 3-electrode electrochemical cell was used. The anodic peaks attributable to the oxidative dissolution of AuZn_x alloys are labeled in the corresponding charts. The arrow indicates the redox potential of the Au³⁺/Au⁺ couple.

surface. (This finding could be of prospective practical interest, e.g., in gold mining to avoid the cyanidation of gold ore). As in the previous case of Mn-electrochemistry (Section 3.1), there is no obvious interference of the Zn plating/stripping with Au-electrochemistry occurring at potential from ca. 0.7 to 2.5 V_{Zn}. In other words, the Au-surface, which was pretreated by Zn-deposition and its subsequent stripping, behaves like a virgin gold surface (Fig. 4A). (Note, however, specific effects on the Zn-stripping at potentials <0.7 V_{Zn}, which will be discussed later).

The anodic dissolution of gold in the WiSE to AuCl₄ was further confirmed by in situ Raman spectroelectrochemistry. At 2 V_{Zn}, two distinct bands at 324 and 347 cm⁻¹ appear on the Au electrode (Fig. S14 B), which are assigned to the symmetric (A_{1g}) and asymmetric (B_{1g}, B_{2g}) Au-Cl stretching modes of the AuCl₄ (cf. Eqs. 12–14) [60]. To verify that these bands originate from the gold dissolution, rather than from other changes at the electrochemically treated interface, comparative measurements were performed on an HOPG electrode (Fig. S14 A1, A2). In this case, no bands were observed within the entire potential range, while both the electrolyte band at ca. 290 cm⁻¹ (assigned to ZnCl₄²⁻) and the G band of HOPG (1580 cm⁻¹) remained unchanged. This is consistent with the cyclic voltammogram (Fig. S3), confirming that there are no apparent faradaic reactions at blank HOPG in the range from ca. 0.4 to 2.5 V_{Zn}. The tetrahedral ZnCl₄²⁻ is the dominant species in 15 m WiSE [47]. These tetrahedra are interconnected by Cl-atoms into agglomerates at larger concentrations (>25 m) [47].

The Raman features detected on Au arise directly from the formation

of AuCl₄ (Fig. S14 B, C) generated during the anodic oxidation of the gold surface. The onset of AuCl₄ formation appears at 2 V_{Zn}, which is consistent with the corresponding voltammograms (Figs. 4, 5A, S3, and S13), and allows for deconvolution of the anodic wave, in which several reactions are superimposed (cf. Eqs 12–17 below).

The electrochemistry of AuCl₄ on a glass-like carbon electrode in ionic liquid was studied by Aldous et al. [46]. The two-electron reduction starts at ca. 1.5 V_{Zn}:

Reaction (12) is followed by one-electron deposition of gold:

Alternatively, the Au(I) species is prone to disproportionation:

The oxidative sweep is dominated by an asymmetric peak near 2 V_{Zn} which is assignable to Au(0) re-oxidation associated with subsequent oxidation of chloride:

Fig. 5. H-cell tests in 15 m ZnCl_2 + 0.1 m HAuCl_4 ; the positive electrode is graphite rod the negative electrode is Zn. [A] Cyclic voltammograms, scan rate 50 mV/s; the first and second scans are depicted by full and dashed curves, respectively. [B, D] galvanostatic charge/discharge ($\pm 2 \text{ mA/cm}^2$) at different stages of cycling; the maximal time for charging was deliberately set at 1 hr. [C] Cycle life for anodic (red points) and cathodic (blue points) currents.

Figs. 4B and C show cyclic voltammograms of HOPG or glass-like carbon, respectively, in 15 m ZnCl_2 + 0.1 m HAuCl_4 . In these cases, we had to use the Ag/AgCl reference and Pt-counter electrode, because HAuCl_4 reacts with metallic Zn. This perturbation was avoided (at least temporarily) in an H-shaped cell, in which the Zn-counter-electrode was separated from the carbonaceous working electrode by a glass-fiber separator (Fig. 4D; for the set-up see Fig. S15 in ESI). Interestingly, the anodic wave between -0.75 and $0 \text{ V}_{\text{AgCl}}$ now splits into several peaks at -0.66 , -0.58 , -0.38 and $-0.18 \text{ V}_{\text{AgCl}}$, both for the HOPG and the glass-like carbon electrodes. Similar splitting can also be traced in the H-cell (Fig. 4D) and in other cases (Fig. S3 in ESI).

This effect is specific to the Au-containing media only, i.e., blank WiSE and WiSE with Mn^{2+} exhibit solely one single-peak of Zn-stripping (Figs. 1, 3, S3, S10–12). This can be attributed to the formation of multiple Au-Zn alloy phases at the carbon surface. These alloys form as a result of the much lower redox potential of the Zn/Zn^{2+} couple compared to the $\text{Au}^{3+}/\text{Au}^+$ and Au^+/Au couples (see below), which drives the reduction of Au^{3+} and concurrent alloying with Zn. Under anodic polarization, the different Au-Zn phases dissolve sequentially, giving rise to distinct dissolution steps.

More specifically, three different alloys AuZn and AuZn_3 (cubic) and $\text{Au}_{1.2}\text{Zn}_{8.8}$ (hexagonal) have been identified by diffraction of synchrotron radiation at the Au-electrode in an ionic liquid containing ZnCl_2 [61]. To avoid parasitic H_2 -evolution, the Zn-Au alloying has been studied so far in aprotic imidazolium-based ionic liquids [61,62]. It manifested itself by four sharp anodic peaks in the potential region extending approx. 0.5 V positive to the formal potential of Zn^{2+}/Zn . A close similarity with our voltammogram (Fig. 4) supports a hypothesis,

that these reactions also occur on carbon electrodes in $\text{HAuCl}_4 + \text{ZnCl}_2$ (WiSE). Additional arguments in favor of electrochemical alloying/de-alloying of AuZn_x follow from XPS (Fig. S16), SEM images and EDX (Fig. S17). EDX and XPS consistently confirm the ZnAu_3 stoichiometry, which is reminiscent of the tetragonal ($I4_1/acd$) intermetallic phase of the same composition [63,64].

Fig. 4 further allows for independent comparison of reference potentials (see Eq. 8 and Section 3.1). The formal potential at which the current of Zn(Au) plating/stripping flips from negative to positive equals $-0.81 \text{ V}_{\text{AgCl}}$ or 0 V_{Zn} . The calculated $E_{\text{WiSE}}^{\text{Zn}}$ was -0.73 V vs. SHE (Eq. 8), which translates into $-0.927 \text{ V}_{\text{AgCl}}$ (for the Ag/AgCl potential of 0.197 V vs. SHE). The difference (0.117 V) of the measured vs. calculated potentials of the Zn^{2+}/Zn and the Ag/AgCl reference electrodes is a specific signature of WiSE. In addition to the Nernstian shifts (effects of concentration and activity coefficients; Eq. 8), the liquid junction potential between the WiSE and the reference electrode also contributes to the observed discrepancy [51].

To provide a coherent overview of all the potential shifts, Figure S18 replots representative voltammograms of Au- and Mn-related redox couples on HOPG from Figs. 4 and 1, respectively, together with those of blank HOPG in pure 15 m ZnCl_2 . The figure also includes formal potentials derived from tabulated standard redox potentials. As expected, gold exhibits conventional behavior in our WiSE, which is attributed to the use of a chloro-complex precursor (HAuCl_4). In contrast, Mn-related redox potentials are downshifted relative to the tabulated data, consistent with the formation of chloromanganate species. Zinc, on the other hand, displays an upward potential shift, arising from the combined effects of chloro-complexation and WiSE-specific phenomena.

To further address these multifaceted effects, Fig. S19 compares the electrochemical response of two model redox couples, $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+/2+}$ and $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+/2+}$ ($\text{bpy} = 2,2'$ -bipyridine) in 15 m ZnCl_2 (WiSE), referenced to measurements in a “normal” electrolyte concentration of 0.1 m ZnCl_2 . The $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+/2+}$ couple remains largely unaffected by ZnCl_2 concentration, whereas $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{3+/2+}$ couple exhibits a pronounced downshift in the WiSE. These observations identify $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+/2+}$ as a convenient redox probe for experimentally referencing redox potentials in WiSE, analogous to the use of ferrocene as an internal reference in aprotic media.

Fig. 5 summarizes the data from our tests in a two-electrode (H-cell) using a graphite rod electrode in contact with 15 m $\text{ZnCl}_2 + 0.1$ m HAuCl_4 . Additional data for the glass-like carbon electrode are shown in Fig. S20 (ESI). The voltammetric peaks are broad and asymmetric, but the observed formal redox potential around 1.6–1.7 V_{Zn} agrees reasonably well with the standard potentials listed above (≈ 0.9 –1.1 V_{SHE}).

The cyclic voltammogram (Fig. 5A) provides anodic and cathodic areal charges of 62 and 73 $\mu\text{Ah}/\text{cm}^2$, respectively (85 % reversibility). Interestingly, the found charging disbalance is now opposite, as compared to that for Mn-containing WiSE (cf. Fig. 3 and Section 3.2). Hence, at the relatively fast voltammetric cycling, the main parasitic reactions are assumed to be anodic for the Au-containing WiSE and cathodic for the Mn-containing WiSE.

On the other hand, at the slower galvanostatic cycling, the anodic breakdown is always dominating for both the Au- and Mn-based systems (Figs. 3B–D, 5B–D). The cycling irreversibility for Au-containing WiSE is presumably related to the oxidation of chlorides (Eqs. 15–17). In the case of Mn-containing WiSE, the oxidative breakdown is more complicated, because it is interfaced to the formation of MnO_2 and MnO_4 (Eqs. 5–7), but the terminating chlorine evolution (Eqs. 15–17) could be at play, too.

Despite the mentioned problems, the cycle life of our hybrid Zn/Au system is quite good: Fig. 5C shows that there is no fading of cathodic capacity over 70 cycles, when the areal discharge capacity stabilizes at approximately 1.2 mAh/cm^2 . This is roughly comparable to the capacity of the hybrid Zn/Mn-battery discussed in Section 3.2, and exceeds again, by order of magnitude, the areal capacity of a traditional Zn-ion battery.

4. Conclusions

Zn-ion battery with a redox mediator (MnCl_2) dissolved in 15 m ZnCl_2 represents a promising route toward safe, simple and efficient energy storage. An inert carbonaceous electrode surrounded by a mm-thick solution layer can provide larger areal storage capacities compared to traditional positive electrodes, which rely on solid-state active materials (e.g., phosphate olivines). Areal capacities of ~ 1 mAh/cm^2 can be maintained over tens of cycles. This capacity is available in a WiSE volume, which would fit the standard 2032 coin cell.

Stable and reversible charging/discharging of Mn-based systems relies on the formation of γ - MnO_2 over a broad potential window. Moreover, optical and Raman spectroscopy support the hypothesis that permanganate, transiently generated at higher potentials, is rapidly quenched via comproportionation with Mn^{2+} . Overall, the WiSE environment substantially mitigates the formation of “dead MnO_2 ”. Charge transfer is governed by simple diffusion with the Mn^{2+} diffusion coefficient primarily constrained by the electrolyte viscosity.

The electrochemistry of Au in 15 m ZnCl_2 closely parallels that of Mn, such that the two redox couples can be easily mistaken. Both the Mn- and Au-containing systems produce asymmetric cyclic voltammograms with broad peaks around the formal potential of ~ 1.7 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn . While the Au-redox processes occur close to their expected standard redox potentials, the Mn redox couples are shifted downward by ~ 0.7 V. This shift arises from chloromanganate formation in combination with WiSE-specific effects. The potentials in WiSE are conveniently referenced to the $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+/2+}$ couple, which is essentially insensitive to ZnCl_2 concentration. Accordingly, this particular redox couple is

recommended as a reference system for reporting potentials in WiSE systems.

Gold undergoes rapid dissolution in 15 m ZnCl_2 above ~ 2.0 V vs. Zn^{2+}/Zn , with a dissolution rate roughly twice that of Zn under the same conditions. In situ Raman spectroelectrochemistry confirms that AuCl_4 formation is triggered at ~ 2.0 V_{Zn} , consistent with oxidative dissolution pathways. The formation of Au–Zn intermetallic phases is detectable from distinct anodic features appearing in the anodic part of cyclic voltammograms. It is further confirmed by XPS, SEM and EDX analyses, which evidence the formation of uniform nanograins of the Au_3Zn composition.

Data availability

Data are available at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17984616>

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ladislav Kavan: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Tařana Supinkova:** Investigation, Data curation. **Věra Mansfeldova:** Investigation, Data curation. **Markěta Zukalova:** Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Zuzana Vlčkova Živcova:** Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Felix T. Eickemeyer:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Michael Graetzel:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the project “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research, by the Czech Science Foundation (grant No. 23–05895S) and by the Research Infrastructure NanoEnviCz, Project No. LM2023066 and Pro-NanoEnviCz (Reg. No. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_013/0001821). L.K. thanks the Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne for support under a visiting professor’s appointment at the Institute of Chemical Science and Engineering (ISIC). The authors are grateful to Lenka Belhacova for providing SEM/EDX images, Ludmila Simkova for UV–Vis spectra, and Michael Vorochta for XPS measurements.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2026.148513](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2026.148513).

References

- [1] T. Shoji, M. Hishinuma, T. Yamamoto, Zinc-manganese dioxide galvanic cell using zinc sulphate as electrolyte. Rechargeability of the cell, *J. Appl. Electrochem.* 18 (1988) 521–526.
- [2] C. Xu, B. Li, H. Du, F. Kang, Energetic zinc ion chemistry: the rechargeable zinc ion battery, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 51 (2012) 933–935.
- [3] J.R. Loh, J. Xue, W.S.V. Lee, Challenges and strategies in the development of zinc-ion batteries, *Small. Methods* 7 (2023) e2300101.
- [4] S.W.D. Gourley, R. Brown, B.D. Adams, D. Higgins, Zinc-ion batteries for stationary energy storage, *Joule* 7 (2023) 1415–1436.
- [5] D. Patel, A.K. Sharma, Minireview on aqueous zinc–sulfur batteries: recent advances and future perspectives, *Energy & Fuels* 37 (2023) 10897–10914.

- [6] Y. Ran, F. Dong, S. Sun, Y. Lei, Aqueous zinc-based batteries: active materials, device design, and future perspectives, *Adv. Energy Mater.* (2025) 2406139.
- [7] A. Konarov, N. Voronina, J.H. Jo, Z. Bakenov, Y.-K. Sun, S.-T. Myung, Present and future perspective on electrode materials for rechargeable zinc-ion batteries, *ACS Energy Lett.* 3 (2018) 2620–2640.
- [8] Z. Khan, D. Kumar, X. Crispin, Does water-in-salt electrolyte subdue issues of Zn batteries? *Adv. Mater.* 35 (2023) e2300369.
- [9] J. Wei, P. Zhang, J. Sun, Y. Liu, F. Li, H. Xu, R. Ye, Z. Tie, L. Sun, Z. Jin, Advanced electrolytes for high-performance aqueous zinc-ion batteries, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 53 (2024) 10335–10369.
- [10] Y.Y. Hsieh, H.Y. Tuan, Emerging trends and prospects in aqueous electrolyte design: elevating energy density and power density of multivalent metal-ion batteries, *Energy Stor. Mater.* 68 (2025) 103361.
- [11] S. Chen, M. Zhang, P. Zou, B. Sun, S. Tao, Historical development and novel concepts on electrolytes for aqueous rechargeable batteries, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 15 (2022) 1805–1839.
- [12] J. Xie, Y.C. Lu, Designing nonflammable liquid electrolytes for safe Li-ion batteries, *Adv. Mater.* 37 (2025) e2312451.
- [13] L. Suo, O. Borodin, T. Gao, M. Olguin, J. Ho, X. Fan, C. Luo, C. Wang, K. Xu, Water-in-salt[†] electrolyte enables high-voltage aqueous lithium-ion chemistries, *Science* 350 (2015) 938–943.
- [14] C. Zhang, J. Holoubek, X. Wu, A. Daniyar, L. Zhu, C. Chen, D.P. Leonard, I. A. Rodriguez-Perez, J.X. Jiang, C. Fang, X. Ji, A ZnCl₂ water-in-salt electrolyte for a reversible Zn metal anode, *Chem. Commun.* 54 (2018) 14097–14099.
- [15] Y. Zhu, J. Yin, X. Zheng, A.-H. Emwas, Y. Lei, O.F. Mohammed, Y. Cui, H. N. Alshareef, Concentrated dual-cation electrolyte strategy for aqueous zinc-ion batteries, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 14 (2021) 4463–4473.
- [16] Z. Yi, G. Chen, F. Hou, L. Wang, J. Liang, Strategies for the stabilization of Zn metal anodes for Zn-ion batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (2020) 2003065.
- [17] S. Nandi, M. Pumera, Anode free zinc-metal batteries (AFZMBs): A new paradigm in energy storage, *Small* 21 (2025) 2412161.
- [18] B. Zhang, J. Yao, C. Wu, Y. Li, J. Liu, J. Wang, T. Xiao, T. Zhang, D. Cai, J. Wu, Z. W. Seh, S. Xi, H. Wang, W. Sun, H. Wan, H.J. Fan, Electrolyte design for reversible zinc metal chemistry, *Nat. Commun.* 16 (2025) 71.
- [19] Y. Sui, C. Liu, R.C. Masse, Z.G. Neale, M. Atif, M. AlSalhi, G. Cao, Dual-ion batteries: the emerging alternative rechargeable batteries, *Energy Stor. Mater.* 25 (2020) 1–32.
- [20] J. Zheng, Q. Zhao, T. Tang, J. Yin, C.D. Qilty, G.D. Renderos, X. Liu, Y. Deng, L. Wang, D.C. Bock, C. Jaye, D. Zhang, E.S. Takeuchi, K.J. Takeuchi, A. C. Marschilok, L.A. Archer, Reversible epitaxial electrodeposition of metals in battery anodes, *Science* 366 (2019) 645–648.
- [21] T. Supínková, M. Zukalová, N. Kakavas, J. Xu, W. Niu, F.T. Eickemeyer, M. Graetzl, L. Kavan, Electrolyte effects and stability of Zn/Li dual-ion batteries with water-in-salt electrolytes, *J. Power Sourc.* 655 (2025) 237983.
- [22] S. Liu, Z. Liang, H. Zhou, W. Cai, J. Wu, Q. Zhang, G. Yang, W.A. Daoud, Z. Nie, P. Hiralal, S. Luo, G.A.J. Amarantunga, Recent progress in cathode-free zinc electrolytic MnO₂ batteries: electrolytes and electrodes, *Batteries* 11 (2025) 171.
- [23] Z.A. Zafar, G. Abbas, K. Knizek, M. Silhavik, P. Kumar, P. Jiricek, J. Houdková, O. Frank, J. Cervenka, Chaotropic anion based “water-in-salt” electrolyte realizes a high voltage Zn–graphite dual-ion battery, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 10 (2022) 2064–2074.
- [24] J. Han, A. Mariani, A. Varzi, S. Passerini, Green and low-cost acetate-based electrolytes for the highly reversible zinc anode, *J. Power Sources* 485 (2021) 229329.
- [25] X. Zhong, F. Wang, Y. Ding, L. Duan, F. Shi, C. Wang, Water-in-salt electrolyte Zn/LiFePO₄ batteries, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 867 (2020) 114193.
- [26] J.W. Zhao, Y.Q. Li, X. Peng, S.M. Dong, J. Ma, G.L. Cui, L.Q. Chen, High-voltage Zn/LiMn_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}PO₄ aqueous rechargeable battery by virtue of “water-in-salt” electrolyte, *Electrochem. Commun.* 69 (2016) 6–10.
- [27] N. Yesibolatı, N. Umirov, A. Koishybay, M. Omarova, I. Kurmanbayeva, Y. Zhang, Y. Zhao, Z. Bakenov, High performance Zn/LiFePO₄ aqueous rechargeable battery for large scale applications, *Electrochim. Acta* 152 (2015) 505–511.
- [28] Y. Wang, B. Guo, S. Duan, Y. Zhang, Highly stable zinc anode enabled by a Zn-ion-regulating interface for Zn metal batteries, *J. Power Sources* 655 (2025) 237974.
- [29] F. Wang, O. Borodin, T. Gao, X. Fan, W. Sun, F. Han, A. Faraone, J.A. Dura, K. Xu, C. Wang, Highly reversible zinc metal anode for aqueous batteries, *Nat. Mater.* 17 (2018) 543–549.
- [30] C. Zhang, W. Shin, L. Zhu, C. Chen, J.C. Neuefeind, Y. Xu, S.I. Allec, C. Liu, Z. Wei, A. Daniyar, J.X. Jiang, C. Fang, P. Alex Greaney, X. Ji, The electrolyte comprising more robust water and superhalides transforms Zn-metal anode reversibly and dendrite-free, *Carbon Energy* 3 (2020) 339–348.
- [31] N. Rampal, H.-W. Wang, D. Biriukov, A.B. Brady, J.C. Neuefeind, M. Predota, A. G. Stack, Local molecular environment drives speciation and reactivity of ion complexes in concentrated salt solution, *J. Mol. Liquids* 340 (2021) 116898.
- [32] J. Huang, X. Chi, J. Wu, J. Liu, Y. Liu, High-concentration dual-complex electrolyte enabled a neutral aqueous zinc-manganese electrolytic battery with superior stability, *Chem. Eng. J.* 430 (2022) 133058.
- [33] Y. Wang, Q. Li, H. Hong, S. Yang, R. Zhang, X. Wang, X. Jin, B. Xiong, S. Bai, C. Zhi, Lean-water hydrogel electrolyte for zinc ion batteries, *Nat. Commun.* 14 (2023) 3890.
- [34] Y. Zong, H. He, Y. Wang, M. Wu, X. Ren, Z. Bai, N. Wang, X. Ning, S.X. Dou, Functionalized separator strategies toward advanced aqueous zinc-ion batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 13 (2023).
- [35] K. Dong, B. Shen, X. Xie, X. Wang, Y. Jiang, P. Xie, H. Peng, G. Ma, Electrolyte additive strategies for stabilizing Zn anodes in Zn²⁺ energy storage devices, *Batter. Supercaps* (2025) e202500415.
- [36] Z. Dai, R. Chanajaree, C. Yang, X. Zhang, M. Okhawilai, P. Pattanauwat, X. Zhang, G. He, J. Qin, Dual-functional additives boost zinc-ion battery electrolyte over wide temperature range, *Energy Mat. Adv.* 6 (2025) 0139.
- [37] D. Gomez Vazquez, J. Ingenmey, K. Trapp, D. Ciliak, M. Salanne, M.R. Lukatskaya, Extended stability window in water-in-salt electrolytes: understanding the origins, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 147 (2025) 35953–35961.
- [38] C.Y. Chen, K. Matsumoto, K. Kubota, R. Hagiwara, Q. Xu, A room-temperature molten hydrate electrolyte for rechargeable zinc-air batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 9 (2019) 1900196.
- [39] R.J. Wilcox, B.P. Losey, J.C. Folmer, J.D. Martin, M. Zeller, R. Sommer, Crystalline and liquid structure of zinc chloride trihydrate: a unique ionic liquid, *Inorg. Chem.* 54 (2015) 1109–1119.
- [40] X.F. Zhang, X. Ma, T. Hou, K. Guo, J. Yin, Z. Wang, L. Shu, M. He, J. Yao, Inorganic salts induce thermally reversible and anti-freezing cellulose hydrogels, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 58 (2019) 7366–7370.
- [41] J. Lei, Y. Yao, Z. Wang, Y.-C. Lu, Towards high-areal-capacity aqueous zinc–manganese batteries: promoting MnO₂ dissolution by redox mediators, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 14 (2021) 4418–4426.
- [42] X. Liu, Z. Chen, C. Zhang, C. Ding, H. Peng, Y. Cui, Y. Gao, High-areal-capacity manganese-based redox flow batteries via sodium diphosphate/modified electrolyte, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* (2025) 2509495.
- [43] D. Reynard, S. Maye, P. Peljo, V. Chanda, H.H. Girault, S. Gentil, Vanadium-manganese redox flow battery: study of Mn(III) disproportionation in the presence of other metallic ions, *Chemistry Eur. J.* 26 (2020) 7250–7257.
- [44] Y. Ren, H. Li, Y. Rao, H. Zhou, S. Guo, Aqueous MnO₂/Mn²⁺ electrochemistry in batteries: progress, challenges, and perspectives, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 17 (2024) 425–441.
- [45] H.J. Kim, S. Kim, S. Kim, K. Heo, J.H. Lim, H. Yashiro, H.J. Shin, H.G. Jung, Y.M. Lee, S.T. Myung, Gold-nanolayer-derived zincophilicity suppressing metallic zinc dendrites and its efficacy in improving electrochemical stability of aqueous zinc-ion batteries, *Adv. Mater.* 36 (2024) e2308592.
- [46] L. Aldous, D.S. Silvester, C. Villagrán, W.R. Pitner, R.G. Compton, M. Cristina Lagunas, C. Hardacre, Electrochemical studies of gold and chloride in ionic liquids, *New J. Chem.* 30 (2006) 1576–1583.
- [47] T. Yamaguchi, S. Hayashi, H. Ohtaki, X-ray diffraction and Raman studies of zinc (II) chloride hydrate melts, ZnCl₂·RH₂O (r = 1.8, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, and 6.2), *J. Phys. Chem.* 93 (2002) 2620–2625.
- [48] M. Vorochta, V. Mansfeldova, S. Chakraborty, L. Kavan, Work function and electrochemistry of ZnO (wurtzite) single crystals, *Ceram. Int.* 51 (2025) 12346–12354.
- [49] M. Zukalová, M. Vinarčíková, B. Pitná Lásková, L. Kavan, TiO₂ top layer improving the performance of sulfur/carbon composite cathode in Li-sulfur cells, *Materials Chem. Phys.* 296 (2023) 127246.
- [50] H. Lv, Y. Song, Z. Qin, M. Zhang, D. Yang, Q. Pan, Z. Wang, X. Mu, J. Meng, X. Sun, X.-X. Liu, Disproportionation enabling reversible MnO₂/Mn²⁺ transformation in a mild aqueous Zn-MnO₂ hybrid battery, *Chem. Eng. J.* (2022) 430.
- [51] J. Kang, H. Lee, Deciphering potential shifts in highly concentrated LiTFSI aqueous electrolytes, *ACS Electrochem* 1 (2025) 419–424.
- [52] N. Takenaka, S. Ko, A. Kitada, A. Yamada, Liquid madelung energy accounts for the huge potential shift in electrochemical systems, *Nat. Commun.* 15 (2024) 1319.
- [53] M. Schmucker, T.A. Gully, A. Schmidt, B. Schmidt, K. Bromberger, J. Disch, B. Butschke, B. Burgenmeister, K. Sonnenberg, S. Riedel, I. Krossing, Investigations toward a non-aqueous hybrid redox-flow battery with a manganese-based anolyte and catholyte, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (2021).
- [54] M. Bourwina, S. Walha, N. Krayem, R. Badraoui, F. Brahm, W.M. Alshammari, M. Snoussi, M.M. Turnbull, T. Roisnel, H. Naili, Organic-inorganic manganese (II) halide hybrid combining the two isomers cis/trans of [MnCl₄(H₂O)₂]: crystal structure, physical properties, pharmacokinetics and biological evaluation, *Inorganics* 11 (2023) 76.
- [55] A. Li, H. Ooka, N. Bonnet, T. Hayashi, Y. Sun, Q. Jiang, C. Li, H. Han, R. Nakamura, Stable potential windows for long-term electrocatalysis by manganese oxides under acidic conditions, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 58 (2019) 5054–5058.
- [56] C. Hu, Z. Zhao, W. Wang, W. Zou, S. Liu, X. Fang, X. Su, N. Zheng, In situ electrochemical regeneration of permanganate ion for sustainable oxidation reactions, *Joule* (2025) 9.
- [57] D.E. Irish, B. McCarroll, T.F. Young, Raman study of zinc chloride solutions, *J. Chem. Phys.* 39 (1963) 3436–3444.
- [58] R.C. Dutta, S.K. Bhatia, Structure and ion transport in super-concentrated water-in-salt electrolytes: insights from molecular dynamics simulations, *Electrochim. Acta* (2023) 462.
- [59] S. Lee, M. Kim, J. Park, J. Choi, J. Kang, M. Park, A high voltage aqueous zinc-vanadium redox flow battery with bimodal tin and copper clusters by a continuous-flow electrometallic synthesis, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15 (2023) 7002–7013.
- [60] P.J. Murphy, M.S. LaGrange, Raman spectroscopy of gold chloro-hydroxy speciation in fluids at ambient temperature and pressure: a re-evaluation of the effects of pH and chloride concentration, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 62 (1998) 3515–3526.
- [61] D. Borissov, A. Pareek, F.U. Renner, M. Rohwerder, Electrodeposition of Zn and Au-Zn alloys at low temperature in an ionic liquid, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 12 (2010) 2059–2062.

- [62] J.F. Huang, I.W. Sun, Fabrication and surface functionalization of nanoporous gold by electrochemical alloying/dealloying of Au/Zn in an ionic liquid, and the self/assembly of L/cysteine monolayers, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 15 (2005) 989–994.
- [63] Z.L. Schaefer, D.D. Vaughn, R.E. Schaak, Solution chemistry synthesis, morphology studies, and optical properties of five distinct nanocrystalline Au–Zn intermetallic compounds, *J. Alloy Comp.* 490 (2010) 98–102.
- [64] R. Todorov, T. Hristova-Vasileva, V. Katrova, A. Atanasova, Silver and gold containing compounds of p-block elements as perspective materials for UV plasmonics, *ACS. Omega* 8 (2023) 14321–14341.